

**Activating Istisna'a in Islamic banks to finance housing for people with
limited income - the case of Jordan –**

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Abstract

This study aimed to demonstrate the effectiveness of the Istisna contract in financing the housing sector for low-income people in Jordan, and an attempt to activate this formula in Islamic banks. The contribution to the provision of housing comes on top of social services. Where the descriptive and analytical approach was used, the study population consisted of all workers in Jordanian Islamic banks for the academic year 2019, the study sample consisted of (384) workers in Jordanian Islamic banks, who were chosen randomly. The results of the study showed that the Istisna contract is of great economic importance and is considered an important tributary of economic activity (commercial, industrial, and agricultural). The Istisna'a formula is considered one of the best banking formulas that is compatible with supply contracts. While the results of the survey came from the viewpoint of the study community, the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing. For low-income people in Jordan, through Jordanian Islamic banks, to a moderate degree.

Keywords: housing, Islamic banks, Istisna'a, parallel Istisna, people with limited income.

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that the housing sector is one of the important sectors in the economy, and this importance emerges from both economic and social aspects, due to its role in filling this human need related to housing. The community, especially those with limited incomes, in addition to the fact that most of the finances currently available are finances based on forbidden usury, an extension that introduced another dimension that affected the ability of other groups of society to obtain the necessary finance.

Islamic banking has provided many financing formulas aimed at providing the necessary financing for most needs, and this has been proven by practical experience, and in this research we will address one of those formulas, the Istisna'a contract, as a financing formula that provides multiple and appropriate advantages for financing the construction of housing, especially for those with low incomes.

PROBLEM STATEMENT:

The housing sector in Jordan faces multiple problems, as a result of the absence of a banking system capable of financing this sector through appropriate financing formulas for all segments of society, which led to the deprivation of some segments of society from obtaining adequate housing, especially those with limited income. Istisna' contract to solve this problem, and the problem of the study is to answer the following main question: What is the possibility of activating Istisna'a in Jordanian Islamic banks to finance housing for people with limited income.

The following sub-questions are derived from this question:

1. What is the concept of istisna' contract, parallel istisna', and istisna' sukuk, and what is their importance?
2. What is meant by people with limited income and what is their need for housing finance?
3. What is the role of Islamic banks in financing social services?
4. What is the role of the Istisna contract in financing the housing sector?

Hypotheses

This study adopts the following main hypothesis:

The Istisna contract in Islamic banks plays an important role in financing housing construction for people with limited income.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to achieve a set of goals, namely:

Explanation of the importance of the Istisna contract as one of the appropriate Islamic financing forms for financing housing construction

Identifying the social role of Islamic banks and in the housing sector in particular.

Identifying the role of Istisna contracts in operating idle funds in Islamic banks, and its contribution to improving the ability of Islamic banks to compete with other banks.

THE IMPORTANCE OF STUDY:

The importance of this study emerges from the importance of providing housing, which is one of the necessities of life and the biggest social problems in this era, not to mention its impact on increasing the percentage of spinsterhood in the inability to provide housing, at a time when Islamic banks suffer from their surplus liquidity on the one hand and on the other hand they need to Providing services that are considered social, since social services are one of the foundations upon which Islamic banking thought is based and profitable at the same time. Therefore, activating the Istisna'a contract to provide apartments provides these two services and solves many social problems.

TERMINOLOGY OF STUDY:

Islamic Bank: It is the bank whose law of establishment expressly stipulates compliance with the provisions of Islamic Sharia, and not to deal with interest, taking and giving. (Aleabd Alwahaabi, 436, P 36)

Islamic finance: a set of administrative functions related to cash management to enable the institution to implement its objectives and meet its due obligations on time according to the principles of Islamic Sharia. (Salihi, 2016, P 42)

Istisna'a: A contract to sell a non-existent asset that will be built or manufactured according to agreed specifications and will be delivered in the future at a predetermined price. (Mujtabaa, 2017 P 6).

Low-income people: Those with fixed periodic income, such as government employees and retirees. (Asimi 2013 P 49)

Home Finance: Finance provided by banks and directed towards building, renovating and repairing homes. (Asimi 2013 P 53)

Methodology:

In order to address the problem of the study and answer its questions, the researcher used the descriptive inductive approach, by reviewing the literature that dealt with the subject of the study and explaining how the Istisna'a contract can be applied in financing housing construction .

Previous studies:

There are no studies - according to the researcher's knowledge - that dealt with activating the Istisna contract formula in Islamic banks to finance the housing sector for people with limited income in Jordan, but there are studies that dealt with aspects of the subject of the study, including:

A study (Alrishawin, 2012) dawr albnuk al'iisliamiat fi tamwil qitae al'iiskan fi al'urduni. This study aimed to clarify the role of Islamic banks in Jordan in financing the housing sector, and the researcher chose as the study sample all Islamic banks operating in Jordan. The study found that the resources of Islamic banks are important in financing the housing sector, and this importance is for both the bank and its customers, and the study called for the bank to fail in the guarantees it requires without compromising the bank's rights, and to increase the payment period to reduce the monthly installment to increase the number of beneficiaries of this kind. of financing.

(Bikush study, 2014): "alsiyagh albankiat alhadithat litamwil qitae alsakan fi aljazayir - dirasat halat wikalat alsunduq alwatanii liltawfir walaihtiat - bank eayn fikrun, wawikalat alsunduq alwatanii lilsakan". This study aimed at the role of the banking sector in financing the housing sector in Algeria and its supportive role for the government role in this field. affordable housing for citizens.

Study (Aleumari, 2013): "Altamwil al'iislamiu liqitae alsakan fi aljazayir "This study aimed to clarify the role of Islamic finance in addressing the housing crisis in Algeria as an alternative to usurious financing and through a group of legal contracts such as the Salam and Istisna contracts. The study found that the diversity offered by Islamic finance, especially in the field of real estate finance, in contracts such as Istisna'a and Salam, and this has an impact on solving the housing problem that Algerian society suffers from. , especially those with low incomes, in addition to achieving a high level of flexibility in the methods and tools of real estate financing

The study (Rahi: 1996) "dawr aliaytiman almasrifii fi tamwil suq alsakn fi aleiraqi". This study aimed to clarify the role of housing loans granted by local financial institutions, in financing the credit gap in the housing market, filling the demand for directed housing loans, and assisting banks in finding an outlet for their available liquidity by investing in new purposes, increasing their returns, and ensuring the improvement of their performance indicators. The study found the role of bank credit in financing the housing market in Iraq on the one hand, and these loans contribute to raising the purchasing power of low-income earners to enable them to construct their housing units

What distinguishes this study:

This study is distinguished from other previous studies as a specialized study that shows the ability of Islamic banking to provide financing formulas that help low-income earners to provide adequate housing at reasonable costs, as this study focuses on the Istisna formula as an effective tool in this aspect.

Determinants of the study: This study will be limited to:

- One of the legal contracts that the researcher sees as being compatible with legitimacy for this type of financing, which is the Istisna contract in Islamic banks.
- The category of low-income employees of the public and private sector whose institutions provide them with housing funds, but they are not sufficient for housing.
- All employees of Jordanian Islamic banks in the period 2019

THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE ISTISNA CONTRACT

In this topic, the concept of the parallel Istisna' and Istisna' contract in Islamic banks will be discussed, its importance and the extent of its legitimacy in order to inform the research on how this contract contributes to financing this housing sector for people with limited income, through the following branches:

FIRST: THE CONCEPT OF ISTISNA' CONTRACT.

The supply contract is one of the old contracts that were mentioned in the books of the early jurists, and they quoted it from the practical Sunnahs of the Prophet, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, unlike the modern parallel contract of Istisna', which is a modern term that people need, and is applied in Islamic banks.

THE CONCEPT OF ISTISNA' CONTRACT:

In the language: Ibn Manzur defined it as: making: a craftsmanship that he does well, so he is made, making: his work. (Ibn Manzur: 1980 vol. 8, p208) The Almighty said: "And We taught him the fashioning of coats of armor to protect you from your [enemy in] battle. So will you then be grateful" (Alanbia: 80)

In terminology: The jurists differed in the definition of the Istisna'a contract based on their adaptation to this contract. The Hanafis considered it a separate contract with its terms and conditions (Al-Kasani, 1986: Part 5: p 2). As for the majority of jurists (Maliki, Shafi'i and Hanbali), they included it in the Salam contract when they spoke. About Salam or Salam in industries, and they stipulated for it what they stipulate for the Salam contract, such as accelerating the price and delaying the appraiser, and the Istisna' contract is defined as "a contract on a sale in trust in which work is stipulated in a specific way for a known price", (Aleatiqi, 2015 p 36) or it is "a sale contract in which the work is stipulated on In particular, the raw materials are required to be from the manufacturer, (Maseud, p267) so it can be said that the Istisna'a contract is a contract between two parties, one of which is called the manufacturer and the other is the manufacturer, for the manufacture of something with specific specifications at a specific date and at a known price, provided that the price is delivered now and the appraiser later, and the Istisna'a contract has parties. Which (Maseud, p267):

Manufacturer", (Aleatiqi, 2015 p 59): The party who is obligated to provide the thing to be manufactured.

Al-Mustisna': He is the purchasing party in the Istisna' contract

Contracted: They are the shop and the price.

Formula: It is the offer and acceptance.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ISTISNA CONTRACT:

The importance of the istisna contract is highlighted by the urgent need for it at the present time, as humans vary among themselves in qualities and abilities, and in this the Almighty says: "Do they distribute the mercy of your Lord? It is We who have apportioned among them their livelihood in the life." of this world and have raised some of them above others in degrees [of rank] that they may make use of one another for service. But the mercy of your Lord is better than whatever they accumulate." (Az-Zukhruf: 32), so it can be said that the Istisna' contract is one of the forms of human labor to each other. Through the following: (Hindi 2008 p49)

1-From the side of the manufacturer: the manufacturer is aware that what he will make has already been sold and made a profit, so he works with tranquility, guidance and insight. He may lose out on the sale after that.

2- From the point of view of the manufacturer: As for the one who seeks istisna'a, he has many benefits, the most important of which is that he gets what he wants in the quality and type he wants, so he does not have to buy what may not suit his need and desire from other ready-made goods, and some of the needs may not be ready. Rather, it is necessary to order custom-made, such as houses and buildings, in addition to the fact that the manufacturer continues to manufacture himself, making sure that there is no defect or fraud during this stage, which makes him comfortable and reassuring.

3- From the community side: The Istisna contract contributes to the movement of funds and contributes to reviving the economic movement in the country, especially if the two parties to the contract are from the same country, and this contract also plays a role in emptying each person of competence to his jurisdiction.

VARIETIES OF ISTISNA'A CONTRACT

The Istisna contract has several images in terms of application, and these images are:

1. Istisna': In this type, customers ask the bank to manufacture a specific and specific commodity.
2. Parallel Istisna': It is a contract developed by Islamic banks and this type includes two separate contracts: in the first contract, the bank is a manufacturer of another party that needs commodities, and the other is a manufacturer.
3. sukuk Istisna'a: They are sukuk developed by Islamic banks, and they are defined as "documents of equal value issued with the aim of using their proceeds in the

manufacture of a specific commodity so that the product becomes the property of the sukuk holders”.

Financing advantages of the Istisna contract

As we mentioned earlier, the Istisna'a contract is one of the old contracts known in Islamic jurisprudence, and after the emergence of Islamic banks, amendments were made to this contract to suit the conditions in which Islamic banks operate, and this contract has many financing advantages, which can be mentioned as follows:

1. This contract allows Islamic banks to contribute to the financing of various projects in the community, through the advantages that distinguish it.
2. The Istisna contract secures the various production and consumer goods that society needs.
3. The Istisna contract is considered one of the real financing operations that generate income, unlike some types of contracts that do not generate income. In the economy, in other words, it can be said that the Istisna'a contract contributes to moving the wheel of the economy: the Istisna'a contract finances real projects that contribute to generating incomes, increasing demand and saving money for community service and providing new job opportunities.
4. Istisna' contract enables Islamic banks to operate their available liquidity in projects that benefit them.
5. Flexibility in payment : In the current bank application of this contract, an industrial contract parallel to the original contract can be organized, which allows flexibility in the method of paying the price so that a financing opportunity is available to the seller and buyer at the same time.
6. The multiplicity of the characteristics of this contract: it combines the characteristics of the lease contract in the work and the installment of the wage, and the feature of the Salam contract in the permissibility of delivery of the sale later.
7. The Istisna contract allows the price to be a specific benefit, so that the price is the benefit of the assets that will be manufactured, as in the operation and transfer of ownership projects (B.O.T) through the establishment of projects for which there is no budget.
8. Shortening the operational cycle of the industrial establishment: where the Istisna'a contract reduces the production and marketing costs and credit risks of the establishment because the product is originally sold in addition to the possibility of paying the price in installments.

9. The Istisna contract contributes to supporting long-term financing formulas in Islamic banks.
10. Bearing the responsibility for the appearance of defects in the product made from the alghanam bialgharm walkhiraaj bialdaman, and this is what distinguishes legal contracts from usurious contracts based on a loan
11. The Istisna contract contributes to finding integration between manufacturing expertise and capital.
12. This contract contributes to the non-stagnation of goods and their proper disposal.
13. Istisna'a has a role in developing small industries and replacing imports in the economy with exports.

THE HOUSING SITUATION IN JORDAN:

Housing is one of the indispensable basic necessities of life for individuals, as it achieves security, stability and comfort for the individual. Therefore, the Islamic Sharia has taken care of providing suitable and comfortable housing for individuals and groups. The Almighty said: "And Allāh has made for you from your homes a place of rest" (An-Nahl: 80). We have no work and it has no home, so let it take a home: ... (), as the man-made regulations are concerned with housing insurance, as it was stated in Article 25 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights issued pursuant to the General Assembly resolution in 1948: "The states parties to this covenant recognize the right of a person to A sufficient standard of living for himself and his family, providing what meets their needs of food, clothing and shelter, and his right to a continuous improvement of his living conditions(eulwan 2005, p88) housing is one of the most expensive consumer goods.

Today, housing occupies one of the most important sectors that countries seek to secure due to its direct connection with the social and economic aspects and the level of well-being experienced by it on the one hand and on the other hand to secure the increasing demand for housing due to population increase and internal and external migration processes.

And Jordan, as one of the developing countries with an increasing need for housing, has given the housing sector a priority and considered it the most important productive sector due to the population increase it suffers from, as the population increase in it is one of the highest rates in the world, reaching 5.3%, and its exposure to successive cases of displacement from neighboring countries, which raised the number of The population of Jordan by the end of 2019 reached (10,554) people. (dayirat

alياهو'at aleamati 2019) This increase reflected negatively on the housing situation in Jordan and caused an increase in demand with limited supply.

In response to the increasing housing needs, it established the first governmental institution, the Housing Corporation, in 1967, and its establishment was the beginning of the government's direct intervention in providing adequate housing. In 1980, the government established the Urban Development Department to implement urban development projects and improve low-income and slum neighborhoods and provide them with social services. (Almuasasat Aleamat Waltatwir Alhadariu, (2016 - 2010)) And because the state alone cannot secure housing, it opened the way for the private sector to take its role. One was known as the General Organization for Urban Development in 1992 for this purpose, and opened the way for banks, particularly the Population Bank, to provide housing loans to individuals.

Since its inception, the General Organization for Urban Development has achieved multiple achievements that enabled large segments of Jordanian society to own adequate housing, as it completed about 66 thousand housing units within (286) housing projects distributed over all governorates of the Kingdom, within the following axes:

Implementation of (189) projects that included approximately (42) thousand housing units, of which about (20) thousand apartments.

-Establishment of Abu Nseir residential city with full infrastructure and superstructure services within two phases that included (6073) housing units Of these, (3650) housing units are built and (2,423) plots of serviced land. In 2016, the city's population reached about (70) thousand people.

Implementation of infrastructure improvement projects for poorly serviced and slum fields and improving their conditions in all respects Social and economic, as it developed (39) sites, benefiting more than (400,000) citizens.

-Implementation of projects directed in partnership with the organized private sector, where the Corporation signed (52) partnership agreements implemented from During this period, about (10) thousand housing units, about (2000) apartments.

Implementation and marketing of the Royal Housing Initiative (a decent housing for a decent living), which was implemented through two main axes (apartments

Residential and Serviced Land) Through them, (8504) apartments were implemented within (11) sites in the main governorates, and (980) plots of land were distributed within (8) sites.

Providing subsidized housing loans to employees through the housing finance support program, where about (6000) employees actually benefited between the years 2000 - 2010.

The researcher believes that despite these achievements and these multiple projects, the beneficiaries of them are certainly not people with limited income due to the high prices and the monthly installments that exceed the financial capacity of this category. Therefore, it is necessary to search for a new formula for financing housing for people with limited income, and this is what we will discuss.

THE ROLE OF THE ISTISNA CONTRACT IN FINANCING THE HOUSING SECTOR FOR PEOPLE WITH LIMITED INCOME.

The Istisna'a contract is considered one of the most suitable financing contracts for financing the housing sector, which can respond to the requirements of the banking profession while maintaining its legal integrity when applied. On the one hand, it responds to Islamic banking thought that aims to provide social services and on the other hand achieve a financial return. Correcting the banking path towards financing real economic activities far from Murabaha, which constitutes the largest percentage in the banking business.

First: How to implement the Istisna contract between the Islamic bank and the housing applicant.

Although the bank can be a manufacturer in most of the works that fall within the Istisna'a contracts, the issue of construction is difficult for Islamic banks to undertake on their own, as it requires continuous monitoring, permanent work, and specialized and numerous cadres, which are not available with Islamic banks. As a manufacturer at the same time (parallel Istisna).

An Islamic bank can apply Istisna'a in housing finance in one of two ways:

The bank being a manufacturer: the housing applicant comes to the bank with accurate specifications for the housing he wants, claiming an engineering drawing and all approvals from the official authorities that there is no impediment to the establishment of housing.

The importance of housing and the need for it for people with limited income

Housing is one of the basic necessities of life that are indispensable to individuals. It achieves security, stability and comfort for the individual. Therefore, the Islamic Sharia has taken care of providing appropriate and comfortable housing for individuals and groups. The Almighty said:)And Allāh has made for you from your homes a place of rest

and made for you ((An-Nahl: 80), and the Messenger promised her of the perfection of life by saying: Who among you becomes safe in his sacking, is healthy in his body, for him has the sustenance of his general day,(albukhari, p47) and he has made his daily food

secure The state: Whoever has a job for us and does not have a home, let him take it (ibn hanbul, p543)

Today, housing occupies one of the most important sectors that countries seek to secure due to its direct connection with the social and economic aspects and the level of well-being experienced by it on the one hand and on the other hand to secure the increasing demand for housing due to population increase and internal and external migration processes.

Jordan, as one of the developing countries, gave the housing sector a priority and considered it one of the productive sectors due to the population increase, which is considered one of the highest rates in the world, reaching 5.3%, and its exposure to successive displacements from neighboring countries, which raised the population of Jordan by the end of 2019 to (10554) people() .

The state established the first governmental institution, the Housing Corporation in 1967, and then the Urban Development Department in 1980, until the two institutions were merged into one institution known as the General Corporation for Urban Development in 1992 AD to enable the private sector to work with it in the field of housing loans

The role of the government and the private sector in financing people with limited income.

SURVEY STUDY:

In the previous presentation, we tried to show the theoretical possibility of activating the Istisna'a contract to finance housing for people with limited incomes. In order for the benefit to be complete and the benefit to be achieved, we preferred to allow a scope for the applied aspect of the survey, so that the benefit would be more general, clearer and more accurate.

Method and Procedure

This part includes a description of the study population and its sample, the tools used for which validity and reliability indications were extracted, the study's variables and procedures, and the statistical treatment that was used to answer the study's questions.

Study Methodology:

The researcher used the descriptive approach to find out the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks

Study Community:

The study population consisted of all employees of Jordanian Islamic banks for the academic year 2019

The Study Sample:

The study sample consisted of (384) workers in Jordanian Islamic banks, who were chosen by random method, and Table No. (1) shows the distribution of the study sample according to personal variables

Table(1)

Distribution of the sample members according to personal variables(384)

Variable	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	181	47
	Female	203	53
	Total	384	100

Study tool:

To answer the study questions, the researcher prepared the study tool, with the aim of identifying the possibility of activating the Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks, where the researcher developed and used the appropriate tool for the nature of the study in collecting the necessary information, which included: a questionnaire. In its final form, the questionnaire consisted of (66) items representing (6) dimensions or fields.

The study tool was developed according to the following steps:

- Reviewing the previous literature related to the topic of the current study, through:

- Reviewing previous studies related to the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks
- Analyzing the collected opinions and information related to the subject of the study.
- Based on previous literature related to the topic, the researcher was able to develop the study tool, which is a questionnaire consisting in its initial form of (70) paragraphs distributed over (7) dimensions, which dealt with identifying the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for people with limited income in Jordan through banks. Jordanian Islamic. It was presented to a number of arbitrators with experience in the field to express their opinion on the appropriateness of these paragraphs. The arbitrators recommended deleting part of these paragraphs, and the paragraphs that agreed to be deleted were deleted 80% of the arbitrators, because these paragraphs do not belong and do not measure the possibility of Activating Istisna'a to finance housing for people with limited income in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks, and it was represented through other paragraphs, and thus the final form was reached from this part of the questionnaire, which included in its final form (66) paragraphs representing the fields, and included the ladder of answering these paragraphs Levels are (very high, high, medium, low, very low) to estimate the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks. The average (1 - 2.33) was adopted to represent a low degree of approval, and the average was adopted (2.34 - 3.67).) to represent a medium degree of approval, and the adoption of the average (3.68 - 5) to represent a high degree of approval.

VALIDITY OF THE TOOL:

The validity of the tool was confirmed by presenting it to ten arbitrators with experience in the field to express their opinion on the appropriateness of these paragraphs. It measure the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks, and it was represented in other paragraphs.

TOOL STABILITY:

The stability of the application was verified by distributing the study tool to a pilot sample consisting of (30) workers from outside the study sample twice with a time difference of (two weeks) and extracting the Pearson Correlation coefficient between

their bikes on both times, with the aim of extracting the reliability coefficient for the test. The application of the equation (Cronbach's alpha), and Table No. (2) illustrates this.

Table(2)

The stability coefficient of the application using the Pearson Correlation method and the stability coefficient of the tool using the (Cronbach's alpha) method

Rank	No.	Range	Average	Standard deviation	Evaluation
1	1	The concept of Istisna'a and its distinction	3.55	0.91	Medium
2	6	Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it	3.45	0.95	Medium
3	4	Banking Istisna'a financing	3.45	0.9	Medium
4	2	Provisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty clause	3.38	0.92	Medium
4	5	Financing the housing sector through the public sector	3.37	0.98	Medium
6	3	Financing the housing sector through the private sector	3.2	0.92	Medium
Total			3.4	0.79	Medium

*Statistical function at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

It appears from table (2) that:

The stability coefficients of the (Chronbach Alpha) method for the study fields ranged between (0.71-0.78), which are high and acceptable values for application purposes;

Most studies indicated that the stability coefficient was accepted (0.060) (Al-Sharif and Al-Kilani, 2007).

Pearson's correlation coefficients for the study fields ranged between (0.74-0.77), which are statistically significant values at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), which indicates the stability of the study tool application.

The ratio of the tool as a whole to the reliability coefficient of the (Cronbach's alpha) method was (0.75), and the application coefficient of the (Pearson) method was.(0.77)

STUDY PROCEDURES:

After completing the construction of the study questionnaire in its final form, the researcher performed the following procedures:

Determining the study population and sample of male and female workers in Jordanian Islamic banks (Jordan Islamic Bank, Arab Islamic Bank, and Safwa Islamic Bank).

The researcher communicated with the study sample and determined the place and time.

The researcher made several visits to Jordanian Islamic banks in order to clarify the mechanism of answering the tool.

Distribute the questionnaire to the study members to fill it out.

Data collection and unloading, the number of which is (400), (16) were excluded due to the lack of completeness of their answers, bringing the total number to.(384)

Entering data on the computer to perform statistical treatments, and extract the results.

STATISTICAL PROCESSING:

Statistical processing of the data was carried out using the (SPSS) program on the computer, and the researcher unloaded the data and performed analyzes on it by using the following statistical methods:

-Cronbach's alpha coefficient to calculate stability.

Frequencies, percentages, calculation of mean and standard deviation, in order to identify the possibility of activating Istisna'a for financing housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks

-To answer the second question, the T-test was used to identify the differences in the gender variable.

RESULTS

This chapter includes the presentation of the results of the study, which aims to identify the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks. The results of the study were presented according to the questions that were asked, which are as follows:

First: The results of the first question: What is the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for people with limited income in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks?

In order to answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the answers of the study sample members were extracted from the fields of the study tool and the tool as a whole, Table No. (3) illustrates this

Table(3)

Averages And Standard Deviations Of The Answers Of The Study Sample Members About The Fields Of The Study Tool And The Tool As A Whole (N = 384).

Rank	No.	Range	Average	Standard deviation	Evaluation
1	1	The concept of Istisna'a and its distinction	3.55	0.91	medium
2	6	Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it	3.45	0.95	medium
3	4	Banking Istisna'a financing	3.45	0.9	medium
4	2	fieldsProvisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty	3.38	0.92	medium

		clause			
4	5	Financing the housing sector through the public sector	3.37	0.98	medium
6	3	Financing the housing sector through the private sector	3.2	0.92	medium
Total			3.4	0.79	medium

It appears from Table No. (3) that the arithmetic averages of the answers of the sample members about the fields of study as a whole ranged between (3.20-3.55), where the “the concept of Istisna’a and its distinction” came in the first place with an arithmetic mean (3.55) and a medium evaluation degree. In the second place, “Financing the housing sector through the private sector” came with an arithmetic average (3.45) with a medium rating score, and in the third place came “FieldsProvisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty clause” with an arithmetic average (3.45) with a medium rating score. The "Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it" and "Financing the housing sector through the public sector" were ranked fourth, with an arithmetic mean (3.37) with a medium rating score, and "Banking Istisna'a" ranked sixth and last. financing" with an arithmetic average (3.20) and a medium evaluation degree, and the arithmetic average of the fields as a whole was (3.39) with a medium evaluation degree.

Second: The results of the second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) due to the gender variable (male and female)?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the opinions of the study sample members were extracted to find out the possibility of activating Istisna’a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through the Jordanian Islamic banks, according to the gender variable. (4) explains it.

Table(4)

The Results Of Applying The Independent Samples T-Test To The Study Areas And The Instrument As A Whole According To The Gender Variable

Field	Gender	mean	Standard deviation	T	Statistical function
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The concept of Istisna'a and its distinction	Male	3.46	0.92	-	0.01
	Female	3.61	0.89	2.45	
Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it	Male	3.3	0.94	-	0.04
	Female	3.43	0.91	2.1	
Banking Istisna'a financing	Male	3.17	0.93	-	0.35
	Female	3.24	0.91	0.49	
Provisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty clause	Male	3.39	0.91	-	0.08
	Female	3.5	0.89	1.77	
Financing the housing sector through the public sector	Male	3.35	0.97	-	0.58
	Female	3.39	0.99	0.55	
Financing the housing sector through the private sector	Male	3.41	0.95	-	0.12
	Female	3.51	0.95	1.45	
Total	Male	3.33	0.8	-	0.07
	Female	3.44	0.78	1.82	

Table (10) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the scores of the study sample in the field The concept of Istisna'a and its distinction according to the gender variable, where the value of (T) reached (-2.45) which is Statistically significant, in favor of females, with a mean (3.61), while the arithmetic mean of males (3.46). There are also statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the degrees of the study sample in the field of Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it according to the gender variable, where the value of (T) reached (-2.10), which is a statistically significant value, In favor of females, it had an average of (3.43), while the mean was (3.30) for males. The table shows that there were no statistically significant differences at the significance

level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the scores of the study sample in the areas Banking Istisna'a financing, fields Provisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty clause, Financing the housing sector through the public sector, Financing the housing sector through the private sector and the tool as a whole according to the gender variable, where (T) values were not statistically significant.

Discussing findings and recommendations

This part includes a presentation to discuss the findings of the current study, and the researcher deals with a set of recommendations in light of the findings of the study.

Discussing the results related to the first question: What is the possibility of activating Istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks?

The results of the study related to this question and received showed the possibility of activating Istisna'a for financing housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks, which were within the average degree of influence, and obtained an arithmetic average of (3.39). The concept of Istisna'a and its distinction came in first with an arithmetic mean (3.54) and a medium rating score, and in second place came the Financing the housing sector through the private sector with an arithmetic average (3.46) with a medium rating score, and in third place came the field FieldsProvisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty clause, with a mean (3.45), with an average rating, and in fourth place, two domains: Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it, and Financing the housing sector through the public sector, with a mean of (3.37) With a medium rating, the field of Banking Istisna'a financing came with an arithmetic average (3.21) and a medium rating, and the arithmetic mean of the fields as a whole was (3.39) with a medium rating, and this study came in agreement with previous studies in general, which theoretically established the possibility of applying and activating Istisna.

Discussing the results related to the second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$ due to the gender variable (male, female)?

The results related to this question indicated that there were statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the scores of the study sample in the field The concept of Istisna'a and its distinction according to the gender variable, where the value of (T) was (-2.45), which is the value of Statistically significant, in favor of females, with a mean of (3.61), while the mean for males was (3.46). There are statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the scores of the study sample in the field Importance of Istisna'a and the need for it according to the gender variable, where the value of (T) (-2.10) is a statistically significant value in

favor of females, with an average Arithmetic (3.43), while the arithmetic mean for males was (3.30), and there were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) between the scores of the study sample in the fields: Banking Istisna'a financing, fieldsProvisions of the Istisna contract and the penalty clause, Financing the housing sector through the public sector, Financing the housing sector through the private sector, and the tool as a whole according to the gender variable. As for its agreement and difference from previous studies, the previous studies did not measure or study the gender factor in this, and this can be attributed to the nature of females and their interest in theoretical issues and their distance from trade and practical practice, so that females depend on the theoretical.

FINDINGS AND RECOMMANDATIONS:

RESULTS:

1. The istisna contract is of great economic importance and is considered an important tributary of economic activity (commercial, industrial, and agricultural).
2. The islamic economic system is distinguished by its superiority over the man-made economic systems in its absorption of all economic developments and making them possible to implement free of legal contradictions.
3. The istisna contract is a real and viable alternative that deals with the issue of delaying the receipt of the two substitutes and the binding promise.
4. The istisna'a formula is one of the best banking formulas that is compatible with supply contracts.

Recommendations:

the study reached a set of recommendations, as follows

1. Conducting more studies to study the possibility of activating istisna'a to finance housing for low-income people in Jordan through Jordanian Islamic banks
2. Launching advertising campaigns to clarify the issues related to the istisna contract and its importance in general and in the residential sector in particular
3. Planning by Islamic banks and the concerned ministries to hold seminars and periodic meetings that focus on istisna because of its great importance in the economic aspects

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